

Estimation of Soaked California Bearing Ratio of Soil Using Machine Learning Methods

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Unstable soil-related disasters are a concern for modern urbanization and development. Hence, it is necessary to stabilize the soil and estimate the geotechnical properties using advanced methodologies, one of the best-suited methods for safe ground to construct any infrastructure. Accordingly, this study has provided machine learning techniques, namely Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines

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(MARS), and Random Forest (RF), to estimate the CBR_s of soil. The dataset used in the study comprised 15 observations. The data consists of input variables including the percentages of fly ash (%FA), cement (%C), and coir fiber (%CF), along with optimum moisture content (OMC), maximum dry density (MDD), and soaked California Bearing Ratio (CBR). The dataset is divided into a training set (55% of the total data) and a testing set (45%). The performance of the developed models was achieved using root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), correlation coefficient (r), and volumetric efficiency (VE). For the training set, MLR achieved RMSE = 1.34, MAE = 1.08, $r = 1.00$, and VE = 0.96, while MARS recorded 7.06, 6.03, 0.92, and 0.77, respectively. In the testing set, MLR again outperformed with 0.86, 0.80, 1.00, and 0.98, compared to MARS, which obtained 3.22, 2.59, 0.99, and 0.92. This study introduces a novel approach by evaluating the predictive capabilities of linear and non-linear machine learning algorithms for soaked CBR estimation using a limited geotechnical dataset, thereby providing insights into model robustness and reliability in data-constrained scenarios.

Keywords: Soil stabilization; Fly Ash; MLR; SVR; MARS; RF.

1. INTRODUCTION

Natural soil is produced from the disintegration or weathering of rocks. However, natural soils, mainly silty sand, soft clay, loose sand, loess, silt, expansive soil, frozen soil, and collapsible soil, can be problematic for geotechnical applications. The engineering properties of soil, such as strength, compressibility, permeability, durability, volume stability, etc, can be improved by soil stabilization. It reduces the void ratio, swelling, permeability, compressibility, and water absorption of soil and then enhances the dry shear strength, density of soil, bearing capacity, and CBR value of soil. The soaked California bearing ratio (CBR_s) of natural soil and soil mixed with different additives is a design parameter. Estimating the CBRs for many transportation applications in the hilly region is essential. This geotechnical property is observed using laboratory tests with some limitations using the Indian Standard code. Prior estimates of the CBR input parameters are required through prediction techniques or tools.

The machine learning method is a sub-area of artificial intelligence (AI) and an area of computer science that concentrates on modeling with available data. It typically focuses on databases associated with applications in different engineering fields to analyze the geotechnical characteristics of soil, soil stability, slope, foundation, water resource management, geoinformatics, financial services, customer resources management, etc. The MLR is a parametric approach, and it can be defined as the linear relationship between two or more independent and dependent variables. A linear regression method was developed for low plasticity silt (ML) and intermediate compressible

silt (MI) soils using variables liquid limit, plastic limit, plasticity index (PI), maximum dry density, and optimum moisture content (Kumar, 2014). The MLR group techniques were used for evaluating the California bearing ratio value of soil for Pakistan from the Atterberg limits, grain size distribution, optimum moisture content, and MDD (Hassan et al., 2021). The MLR models were developed to simulate the CBR value from Atterberg limits, optimum moisture content, and MDD (Sujatha, 2019). In addition, the study was conducted by developing MLR techniques for estimating the CBR value from particle size distribution analysis, OMC, Atterberg limits, and maximum dry density for the soils in Ethiopia and Pakistan (Abdella et al., 2017). The support vector machine, introduced by Vapnik in 1992, is a regression-based and classification-based approach. The SVR approach was used to evaluate the UCS of geopolymer-stabilized clayey soil (Mozumder et al., 2017). The two ML approaches, artificial neural network (ANN) and SVM were used to evaluate the MDD and UCS of cement-stabilized soil by using moisture content (w), liquid limit (LL), plasticity index (PI), sand (S), gravel (G), clay (C), and cement content (CC) as input parameters (Das et al. 2011). The 49 CBR test was performed in stabilized soil in a laboratory, and the data were used for the SVM model. The model's performance was analyzed using the coefficient of determination, and the results were satisfactory ($R^2 = 0.96$) (Sabat, 2015). The multivariate adaptive regression splines were introduced by Friedman in 1991, and it is a statistical approach to developing the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The 51 samples were collected and stabilized by cement, and then, by using an appropriate MARS model, the UCS values were

evaluated by w , liquid limit, plasticity index (PI), percentage of sand (S), percentage of gravel (G), and the CC as input parameters (Suman et al., 2016). The RF and MARS models were developed using numerous data to predict pile drivability (Zhang et al., 2019a; Zhang et al., 2019b). The study establishes Random Forest (RF) as a superior machine learning model for predicting soil cohesion based on fundamental soil parameters, providing a technically robust and efficient alternative to conventional laboratory testing (Ly et al., 2021). The random forest (RF) model can effectively be used for classification and regression analysis. To investigate the feasibility of the RF model in predicting the movement of land surface by including tunnel construction, several researchers used RF to estimate geotechnical engineering problems (Zhou et al., 2016a, 2016b). When many trees are formed in the RF model, the out-of-bag (OOB) error rate reduces, improving the prediction accuracy (Breiman, 1996, 2001). Therefore, RF is widely used to avoid over-fitting and accurately predict the target variable for the bulky dataset in the models (Breiman, 2001).

The present study aims to determine the suitability of machine learning (ML) methods, namely Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS), and Random Forest (RF) for the estimation of the CBR_s of natural soil and soil stabilized using additives namely fly ash, fly ash with cement combinations, and fly ash with coir fiber combinations. To construct and validate the developed ML models, the combination of input variables was the percentage of fly ash, the percentage of cement, the percentage of coir fiber, optimum moisture content (%), and the maximum dry density (%). The performance and competence of the developed ML models were evaluated using statistical parameters, namely root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), correlation coefficient (r), and Volumetric efficiency (VE). This study is novel in its dual focus: firstly, on the comparative performance assessment of linear (MLR) and non-linear (MARS, RF, and SVR) models for predicting soaked California Bearing Ratio (CBR); and secondly, on the implementation of these machine learning algorithms within the constraints of a limited dataset comprising only 15 observations. The work underscores the applicability, challenges, and predictive reliability of data-driven models in low-data geotechnical

contexts where experimental data acquisition is often constrained by high costs, labor intensity, and practical limitations.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area and Data

The soil was collected from Ghurdauri, a hill region located in Pauri Garhwal district in the Himalayan region of Uttarakhand state. Ghurdauri is mainly known for the Govind Ballabh Pant Institute of Engineering and Technology (GBPIET). The map of the study area is shown in Fig. 1. To stabilize the localized soil, the additives were used, such as Class F fly ash, ordinary Portland cement (OPC) of 43 grade, and natural coir fiber. The data were obtained from laboratory investigations on natural and stabilized soil with different additives. A total of 15 data points were included in the study. The data includes percentages of fly ash (%FA), percentages of cement (%C), percentages of coir fiber (%CF), optimum moisture content (OMC), soaked California bearing ratio (CBR_s), and maximum dry density (MDD). The observations are divided into training (55% of the total dataset) and testing sets (45%).

2.2 Methods

The ML techniques, namely MLR, SVR, MARS, and RF models, were developed in the present study to estimate the CBR_s of natural and stabilized soil samples. The methodologies are described below in detail:

2.2.1 Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)

It is a statistically supervised ML technique that predicts the output of several input variables and develops a linear relationship between multiple variables. A regression approach allows production to be forecasted based on two or more predictors. The MLR model's coefficients are fitted using the least square estimation. The MLR model is subject to assumptions of the normality of the error and the linear relationship in the model (Farias et al., 2017). Mathematically, it can be defined as follows:

$$y = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2 + \alpha_3 x_3 + \dots + \alpha_n x_n$$

$$y_i = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i x_i \tag{1}$$

where, α_0 = Intercept coefficient, α_i = Regression coefficient, $i=1,2,3,\dots,n$, y_i = Output and x_i = Input

Study Area Map

Fig. 1. Map of the study area

2.2.2 Support Vector Regression (SVR)

The SVR was introduced by Vapnik in 1992. It is a regression technique based on the same structural risk minimization concept used to evaluate the continuous-valued multivariate functions. The algorithm's function is to map nonlinearly the real data into a higher-dimensional feature space. It is a non-parametric approach using kernel functions for linear and non-linear classification problems. The data points that lie near the hyperplane are support vectors. The support vectors may lie on the boundary line, inside, or outside of the boundary line in the analysis (Vapnik, 1992). An SVM approach is used when the predictive variable involves categorical and continuous data (Tinoco et al. 2014). The Support Vector Machine technique uses the "svm" function of the "e1071" library in R programming software for regression and gives the required statistical parameters for accurate analysis (Markuna et al., 2023). Mathematically, it can be defined as follows:

$$y = w^T \phi(x) + b \quad (2)$$

Where, $w^T = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i$, w = weight vector, b = bias and $\phi(x)$ = nonlinear mapping function of inputs with high dimension

2.2.3 Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS)

The MARS is a nonparametric approach introduced by H. Friedman in 1991 to develop the relationship between the independent and dependent variables, and is independent of the functional relationship. The MARS model is based on the forward pass and backward pass approach. The spline denotes flexible curves joined at the knots (Friedman, 1991). The knot indicates the end region of the data, and next to the beginning for others.

The model is a linear regression type between the two knots. The basis function is a spline or polynomial, including the model's piecewise linear and cubic tasks. In the backward pass approach, redundant basis functions are removed based on generalized cross-validation (GCV) (Sekulic & Kowalski, 1992). Mathematically, the equation for the MARS model can be represented as follows:

$$y = \delta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m \delta_i Y_i(x) \quad (3)$$

Where m is the number of spline functions, $Y_i(x)$ = basis function, δ_i = set of coefficients and, δ_0 = constant

2.2.4 Random Forest (RF)

The algorithm was produced by Leo Breiman in 2001 for both regression and classification. The non-parametric approach operates with numerical and categorical datasets, and the classification is faster than the other models. The regression is similar to the classification tree; the terminal nodes represent the predicted values. In the regression approach of the model, the output is numerically identified, and the training set is derived by the selection of a random distribution of input and output features (Breiman, 2001).

The performance of tree-based approaches is affected by the selection of the pruning process rather than variable selection measures (Pal and Mather, 2003). In the case of bootstrap sampling (bagging), 67% of the data of the original training dataset was contained in the training set, which resulted in one-third of the data being left out in the generation of each tree. This missing data is called out-of-bag data (out of the bootstrap sampling) (Onyelowe et al., 2022). Mathematically, generalization error is defined as follows:

$$MSE_{oob} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i - f_{oob}(x_i)^2 \quad (4)$$

where, $f_{oob}(x_i)$ = OOB estimated for i^{th} observations, and N is no of input variables

2.2.5 Performance Evaluation of ML Techniques

The performance evaluation is necessary to fit the model's goodness and is obtained using statistical parameters such as RMSE, MAE, r , and VE.

2.2.6 Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

The RMSE is used to determine the difference between observed and estimated values. The minimum value of RMSE defines the greater accuracy of estimation. It can be defined as follows:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - E_i)^2}{n}} \quad (5)$$

Where, O_i = i^{th} observed value, E_i = i^{th} estimated value, and n = total observations

2.2.7 Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

It is defined as the average magnitude of the difference between observed and estimated

values and varies between 0 and ∞. It is mathematically defined as follows:

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |O_i - E_i|}{n} \quad (6)$$

2.2.8 Correlation Coefficient (r)

The correlation coefficient can identify the proximity between the observed and estimated values. Its value varies from -1 to 1. The correlation coefficient is mathematically represented as follows:

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O}_i)(E_i - \bar{E}_i)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O}_i)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (E_i - \bar{E}_i)^2}} \quad (7)$$

Where, \bar{O}_i = mean of the observed value, and \bar{E}_i = mean of the i^{th} estimated value

2.2.9 Volumetric Efficiency (VE)

Volumetric efficiency was proposed to avoid some problems associated with Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency. It varies between 0 and 1.

$$VE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (E_i - O_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n O_i} \quad (8)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Properties of the Natural Soil

The engineering properties of natural soil in a quantitative manner are shown in Table 1. The soil is classified as Well Graded Silty Sand (SW-SM) as per IS: 1498-1970. The qualitative representation of the test results of natural soil can be identified in Fig. 2.

Chart 1. The methodology was adopted in the study, as shown below

Table 1. Engineering properties of natural soil

S. No.	Parameters	Results
1.	Liquid Limit	31.625%
2.	Specific Gravity	2.68
3.	Soil type as per IS: 1498-1970	SW-SM
4.	Maximum Dry Density, MDD (gm/cm ³)	1.795 gm/cm ³
5.	Optimum Moisture Content, OMC (%)	9.214%
6.	Soaked California Bearing Ratio, CBR _s (%)	4.605%

Fig. 2. Test Results of Natural Soil (a) Grain Size Distribution Curve of Natural Soil, (b) Flow Curve of Soil, (c) Compaction Characteristics of Natural Soil, (d) Load Penetration Curve of Soaked Soil Sample

3.2 Behavior of CBR_s with Input Parameters

The observed CBR values were collected from laboratory analysis and used as output variables to be estimated through ML techniques, the laboratory test results of natural and stabilized soil, as shown in Table 2.

It was found that with the increase in the percentage of the FA (up to 15% Fly Ash), FAC combination (15% Fly Ash + 6% Cement), and FACF combination (15% Fly Ash + 1.5% Coir Fiber), the OMC of the soil also increases. The

MDD of soil increases with the addition of 5% Fly Ash, 5% Fly Ash+2% Cement, and 5% Fly Ash +0.5% Coir Fiber. The CBR_s of the natural soil was 4.605%. The optimum values of FA (10% Fly Ash) and FACF combination (5% Fly Ash +0.5 % Coir Fiber) were found for CBR_s.

The linear behavior between the input parameters and soaked CBR for training and testing sets is presented in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. For the training set, the CBR value decreases with the increment in the content of Fly Ash and Coir Fiber. In contrast, it increases as the Cement content, OMC, and MDD increase. The fittings of

CBR_s with Fly Ash have relatively lower accuracy. However, the CBR_s and Cement content variation better fit a positive trend for the training set.

Fig. 3. Test Results of Soil Stabilized with Additives (a) Variation of OMC with Percentage of FA, FAC, and FACF, (b) Variation of MDD with Percentage of FA, FAC, and FACF, (c) Variation of CBR_s with Percentage of FA, FAC, and FACF

Table 2. Laboratory Test Results of Natural Soil and Stabilized Soil

S. No.	Mix Used	Parameters		
		OMC (%)	MDD (gm/cm ³)	CBR _s (%)
1.	Soil	9.214	1.795	4.605
	Soil+5% Fly Ash	15.053	1.839	26.763
2.	Soil+10% Fly Ash	16.937	1.821	28.223
	Soil+15% Fly Ash	19.486	1.750	21.897
	Soil+20% Fly Ash	16.781	1.762	12.652

S. No.	Mix Used	Parameters		
		OMC (%)	MDD (gm/cm ³)	CBR _s (%)
3.	Soil+5% Fly Ash+2% Cement	15.845	1.851	44.105
	Soil+10% Fly Ash+4% Cement	18.111	1.779	59.69
	Soil+15% Fly Ash+6% Cement	19.082	1.725	64.121
	Soil+20% Fly Ash+8% Cement	18.775	1.719	85.376
	Soil+5% Fly Ash+0.5% Coir Fiber	12.556	1.848	21.654
4.	Soil+10% Fly Ash+1% Coir Fiber	15.486	1.728	20.194
	Soil+15% Fly Ash+1.5% Coir Fiber	20.059	1.726	16.058
	Soil+20% Fly Ash+2% Coir Fiber	17.918	1.658	7.20

Fig. 4. Linear Behaviour of Input Parameters and CBR_s for Training Set: (a) Fly Ash vs. CBR_s, (b) Cement vs. CBR_s, (c) Coir Fiber vs. CBR_s, (d) OMC vs. CBR_s, (e) MDD vs. CBR_s

For the testing set, the CBR value decreases with an increment in Coir Fiber and MDD content, whereas it increases as the Fly Ash, Cement content, and OMC increase. The fittings

of CBR_s with MDD have relatively lower accuracy. However, the CBRs and cement content variation fit better, with a positive trend for the testing set.

Fig. 5. Linear Behaviour of Input Parameters and CBR_s for Testing Set: (a) Fly Ash vs. CBR_s, (b) Cement vs. CBR_s, (c) Coir Fiber vs. CBR_s, (d) OMC vs. CBR_s, (e) MDD vs. CBR_s

3.5 Comparison of Estimated CBR_s among Different ML Techniques

Statistical analysis is done using R programming software with version 4.1.0, as shown in Table 3. The MLR equation developed for training and testing sets is written as:

For training set:

$$CBR_s = -281.1588 - 0.3827 \cdot FA + 9.5647 \cdot C + 2.4534 \cdot OMC + 146.6335 \cdot MDD \quad (9)$$

For testing set:

$$CBR_s = -74.0587 + 3.8379 \cdot FA - 36.5377 \cdot CF - 0.4902 \cdot OMC + 52.8926 \cdot MDD \quad (10)$$

Where MDD is in gm/cm³ and the rest of the variables are in percentage.

Fig. 6 shows the scatter plot of estimated CBR against observed CBR among different ML

techniques for training and testing sets. All the ML techniques have demonstrated fair accuracy in estimating the CBR value of natural and stabilized soil. However, estimated CBR values are much less scattered using the MLR model than other ML techniques for the training set, with a very high correlation coefficient of 1.0. The estimated CBR values are scattered using the RF model compared to other ML techniques for the testing set, with a correlation coefficient value of 0.95.

In dealing with soil samples used in ML model development with a small dataset, the MLR model has a relatively good relationship to the observed CBR for the training set regarding following the trend line of observed CBR shown in Fig. 7. However, the estimated CBR from SVR and RF models is higher than the observed CBR initially and drops at a certain point. It almost overestimates the observed CBR values. However, the estimated CBR from the MARS model fluctuates much from the observed CBR.

Table 3. Comparison of ML Techniques for CBR Estimation

Technique	Training				Testing			
	RMSE	MAE	r	VE	RMSE	MAE	r	VE
MLR	1.34	1.08	1.0	0.96	0.86	0.80	1.0	0.98
SVR	17.4	13.15	0.83	0.45	7.48	5.56	0.99	0.83
MARS	7.06	6.03	0.92	0.77	3.22	2.59	0.99	0.92
RF	12.97	10.45	1.0	0.61	16.44	13.87	0.95	0.59

Fig. 6. Scatter Plots of (a) MLR for Training Set, (b) MLR for Testing Set, (c) SVR for Training Set, (d) SVR for Testing Set, (e) MARS for Training Set, (f) MARS for Testing Set, (g) RF for Training Set, (h) RF for Testing Set, (i) ML Techniques for Training Set (j) ML Techniques for Testing Set

Fig. 7. Comparison of Observed and Estimated CBR Using (a) MLR for Training Set, (b) MLR for Testing Set, (c) SVR for Training Set, (d) SVR for Testing Set, (e) MARS for Training Set, (f) MARS for Testing Set, (g) RF for Training Set, (h) RF for Testing Set, (i) ML Techniques for Training Set (j) ML Techniques for Testing Set

In addition to the above, it is worth noting that the estimated CBR values from the MLR model are simulated better than other ML techniques for the training sets. The MLR and MARS models have a relatively good relationship to the observed CBR for the testing set, regarding following the trend line of

observed CBR. However, the estimated CBR from SVR and RF models was lower than the observed CBR initially, and at a certain point, it started underestimating the observed values. However, the estimated CBR from the RF model fluctuates much from the observed CBR.

Fig. 8. Comparison of Different Performance Measures between ML Techniques for Training Set: (a) RMSE vs. Models, (b) MAE vs. Models, (c) r vs. Models, (d) VE vs. Models

Fig. 9. Comparison of Different Performance Measures between ML Techniques for Testing Set: (a) RMSE vs. Models, (b) MAE vs. Models, (c) r vs. Models, (d) VE vs. Models

From Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, it can be concluded that MLR and MARS models show better performance in terms of all statistical parameters for both training and testing sets. Hence, the MLR and MARS models can be successfully utilized for estimating the CBR_s of the soil for a small dataset. The enhanced performance of

MLR and MARS models can be attributed to their strong generalization capabilities in data-limited scenarios. MLR, due to its linear structure and low model complexity, is less prone to overfitting, making it well-suited for small datasets where variable relationships are approximately linear. In contrast, MARS, despite being a non-linear

technique, constructs models using piecewise linear basis functions and incorporates automatic variable selection, allowing it to handle limited data effectively without significant overfitting. Conversely, RF and SVR are more complex, high-capacity models that typically require larger datasets to achieve stable and accurate estimations. When applied to small datasets, these models may exhibit overfitting or reduced estimation reliability. As a result, MLR and MARS demonstrate greater robustness and reliability for estimating CBR in geotechnical applications with constrained data availability.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The study shows stabilization of the SW-SM soil with FA, FAC combinations, FAF combinations, and estimation of CBR_s using ML methods. From the study, the following conclusions can be obtained:

1. The ML techniques were developed to estimate CBR_s. From the results, it is concluded that the estimated CBR from SVR and RF models is higher than the observed CBR; it overestimates the observed CBR values for the training set. The estimated CBR from the MARS model fluctuates much from the observed CBR.
2. However, the estimated CBR from SVR and RF models is lower than the observed CBR initially for the testing set. The estimated CBR from the RF model fluctuates much from the observed CBR.
3. It can be concluded that MLR (RMSE=1.34, MAE=1.08, $r=1$, and VE=0.96) and MARS (RMSE=7.06, MAE=6.03, $r=0.92$, and VE=0.77) for the training set and MLR (RMSE=0.86, MAE=0.8, $r=1$, and VE=0.98) and MARS (RMSE=3.22, MAE=2.59, $r=0.99$, and VE=0.92) for the testing set show better performance in terms of all statistical parameters.

DISCLAIMER (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE)

Author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc) and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of this manuscript.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

- Abdella, D., Abebe, T., Quezon, P. E. 2017. Regression analysis of index properties of soil as strength determinant for California Bearing Ratio (CBR). *GSJ* 2017;5 (6):1–12. https://www.scipedia.com/public/Abdella_et_al_2017b.
- Breiman, L. 1996. Bagging predictors. *Mach. Learn.*, 24 (2): 123–140.
- Breiman, L. 2001. Random forests. *Mach. Learn.* 45, 5–32. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010933404324>
- Das, S. K., Samui, P., Sabat, A. K. 2011. Application of artificial intelligence to maximum dry density and unconfined compressive strength of cement-stabilized soil. *Geotechnical and Geological Engineering*, 29(3): 329–342
- Farias, I. G., William Araujo, W., Ruiz, G. 2018. Prediction of California Bearing Ratio from Index Properties of Soils Using Parametric and Non-parametric Models. *Geotech Geol Eng.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10706-018-0548-1>.
- Friedman, J. H. 1991. Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines. *Annals of Statistics*, 19: 1-141.
- Hassan, J., Alshameri, B., Iqbal, F. 2021. Prediction of California Bearing Ratio (CBR) using index soil properties and compaction parameters of low plastic fine-grained soil. *Transp Infrastruct Geotech.* doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40515-021-00197-0>.
- Kumar, D. A. 2014. Study of correlation between California bearing ratio (CBR) value with other properties of soil. *Int J Emerg Technol Adv Eng* 4(1):2250–2459.
- Ly, H. B., Nguyen, T. A., & Pham, B. T. 2021. Estimation of soil cohesion using machine learning method: A random forest approach. *Advances in civil engineering*, (1), 8873993. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8873993>
- Markuna, S., Kumar, P., Ali, R., Vishwakarma A, D. K., Kushwaha, K. S., Kumar, R., Singh, V. K., Chaudhary, S., and Kuriqi, A. 2023. Application of Innovative Machine Learning Techniques for Long-Term Rainfall Prediction. *Pure Appl. Geophys.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00024-022-03189-4>.
- Mozumder, R. A., Laskar, A. I., Hussain, M. 2017. Empirical approach for strength

- prediction of geopolymer stabilized clayey soil using support vector machines. *Construction and Building Materials*, (132) 412–424.
- Onyelowe, K. C., Gnananandarao, T., Ebid, A. M. 2022. Estimation of the erodibility of treated unsaturated lateritic soil using support vector machine-polynomial and -radial basis function and random forest regression techniques. *Cleaner Materials*, (3) 100039. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clema.2021.100039>
- Pal, M., Mather, P.M. 2003. An assessment of the effectiveness of decision tree methods for land cover classification. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 86 (4), 554–565.
- Sabat, A. K. 2015. Prediction of California bearing ratio of a stabilized expansive soil using artificial neural network and support vector machine. *Electron. J. Geotech. Eng.* 20, 981–991.
- Sekulic, S., & Kowalski, B. R. 1992. MARS: A tutorial. *Journal of Chemometrics*, 6, 199–216. doi:10.1002/cem.1180060405
- Sujatha, S. J. 2019. Prediction of CBR from index properties of soil through ANN modelling. *J Emerg Technol Innova Res (JETIR)*, 6(2):287–96.
- Suman, S., Mahamaya, M., Das, S. K. 2016. Prediction of maximum dry density and unconfined compressive strength of cement stabilized soil using artificial intelligence techniques. *International Journal of Geosynthetics and Ground Engineering*, 2(2): 11–22.
- Tinoco, J., Gomes Correia, A., and Cortez, P. 2014. Support vector machines applied to uniaxial compressive strength prediction of jet grouting columns. *Comput. Geotech.*, 55, 132–140.
- Vapnik, V. N. 1992. Principles of risk minimization for learning theory. *In Advances in Neural Information Processing System*, volume 4.
- Zhang, W., Wu, C., Li, Y., Wang, L., Samui, P. 2019b. Assessment of pile drivability using random forest regression and multivariate adaptive regression splines. *Georisk* 114.
- Zhang, W., Zhang, R., Wang, W., Zhang, F., Goh, A.T.C. 2019a. A Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines model for determining horizontal wall deflection envelope for braced excavations in clays. *Tunn. Undergr. Space Technol.* 84, 461-471.
- Zhou, J., Li, X., Mitri, H. S. 2016a. Classification of rockburst in underground projects: comparison of ten supervised learning methods. *J. Comput. Civ. Eng.* 30 (5), 04016003.
- Zhou, J., Shi, X., Du, K., Qiu, X., Li, X., Mitri, H. S. 2016B. Feasibility of Random-forest Approach for Prediction of Ground Settlements Induced by the Construction of a Shield-driven Tunnel. *int. J. Geomech.* 17 (6), 04016129. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)gm.1943-5622.0000817](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)gm.1943-5622.0000817).

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